

CORRECTIONAL SOCIAL WORK PRACTICES IN HANDLING OF PSYCHOSOCIAL PROBLEMS CLIENT OF CORRECTIONAL CASE STUDY IN PALEMBANG CORRECTIONAL HALL (BAPAS)

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Abstract

Correctional Hall (BAPAS) as mandated by the Minister of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia is an institution that provides services to correctional clients by providing social guidance, job training guidance that underwent the Legal Alliance program and the Social Reintegration program. In providing its services, Bapas assigns Correctional Social Work (PK), correctional social work (PK) is the spearhead of socialization in implementing the mandate of RI Law No.12 of 1995 on Equipment System in the field of Counseling, Assistance and Oversight of Outside Correctional Clients. Correctional Social Work (PK) in the execution of duties and functions do not work alone but with other professions such as social workers, psychologists, doctors, religious experts, police, prosecutors and others. Breathing in conducting services prioritizes on the essence of the focus of the problems facing correctional clients, namely the social psychology of correctional clients. Data recorded in the year 2017 Bapas Palembang handle 5 (five) clients with various social problems of psychology. While in this study the authors mengangakat 1 case of domicile family living in Palembang, with the identification of the problem is is not able to interact with the social environment and the illness that is suffered is coughing. The author uses the social work practice approach in the service process that starts with the initial approach that includes engagement, intake and contract, disclosure and understanding of the problem (assessment), preparation of the problem-solving plan (planning), intervention, monitoring & evaluation (evaluation), and ends with termination. The author in the implementation of the process perform several roles in accordance with the needs that occur in solving client problems. The roles of correctional social work used include problem solver, motivator and broker (Intermediaries). In the process of intervention by the author of the client, BAPAS Palembang, the results of changes submitted is the case of the client is still in the process of follow-up that is a). Until now the client has done social guidance on a continuous basis in the nearest LK3. Clients are provided with social services to improve the client's social functioning; b) The client has begun to follow the recitation in his or her current neighborhood to which his neighbors are invited; c) Clients only occasionally mock, because the night wind factor that causes clients often experience cough. In handling the case, the process does not always go according to the author's expectations. There are several obstacles in the implementation process of BAPAS Palembang service to clients. The obstacles include; a) The tendency of the client to survive in his comfort zone, so that takes a long time in the services provided. b) Changing the habits or properties of clients requires a long process, so the intensity of the presence of social workers is high enough to assist clients.

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1. Introduction

The paradigm in the guidance, assisting and supervising of community work is no longer focused on the substance of guidance, assisting and supervising but has shifted to the substance of the implementation of Reintegration of Client in the family and community (family and community resilience). Resilience of Correctional Clients is the ability to solve severe problems, to be able to meet the physical, mental and social needs of clients. A strong indicator of family resilience must be maintained with strong economic resilience, education, morals or religion, and harmony or good family members relationships. When we look at an ecological approach to assess the dynamics of relationships among family members, as well as family members with the environment. Sexual social pressures can happen to individual family members, either to members with problems, who are not able to solve problems, or they have problems from their environment. Environmental conditions that face each other need to understand, because these conditions interconnect or exchange between families and the environment. This can be done by improving the family's ability to utilize the available resources.

Good client issues continue to increase both in quantity and quality, both inside and outside the household that participates in the strengthening of families in families and communities. Some problems in the household include violence, parenting, and marriage. Issues outside the household such as religious, political, socio-cultural and economic conflicts that contribute to family resilience. Each of the people in the family will be looking for their own solutions and their respective worlds. In the end the problem will come and approach them. All this against the psychological or psychological, as well as the ability of social relationships of family members in navigating his life. The family will be socially sustainable, and if it will not seriously affect the family's integrity.

Based on the above problems, people need media to share, consult in order to get solution to the problems faced by correctional clients. Seeing this need, since 2014, the Ministry of Justice and Human Rights through the Directorate General of Corrections has operated 70 Bases in 33 Provinces throughout Indonesia as part of efforts to help find solutions to family problems, especially psychosocial problems. BAPAS as mandated by KEPMENKEH of the Republic of Indonesia Number M.01.PR.07.03 of 1997 concerning the Change of BISPA into BAPAS.

Correctional Hall (BAPAS) is an institution that provides services to correctional clients with Duties include:

1. Conducting Community Research (LITMAS), to:
 - a. Helps facilitate the tasks of Investigators, Public Prosecutors and Judges in Case of naughty Children, both inside and outside the session.
 - b. Helping to complement the data of the Prisoners of Correctional Guidance in coaching, which is seeking approach and contact between the Correctional Residents concerned with the community
 - c. Consideration materials for Head of Correctional Institution in the framework of assimilation process whether or not the Correctional Residents undergo the process of assimilation or Social Integration well.
2. Guiding, assisting and supervising the Correctional Prisoners who are Assimilated or Social Integration (Outside Coaching Institutions), both Family Visiting Leave, Parole and Toward Free
3. Guiding, assisting and supervising misbehavior based on Judgment The Court shall be subject to Criminal, Criminal, Criminal, Final, to State and must follow the Obligatory Work or

Children Assimilated, Family Visit Leave, Parole or Free Leave from Correctional Institution.

4. Holding a Trial Observer Timing Team (TPP) and following the Prison Observation Team Session in correctional institutions / detentions, in order to determine the program of guidance and guidance of prisoners of pemasyarakatan
5. Making Reports and Documentation periodically to the superior Officer and to the agency or other interested parties.
6. Minimize the imposition of criminal sanction on children by suggesting in Community Research, either to the Investigator, Prosecutor or Judge.
7. Holding a Breathing Administration.

Correctional Hall (BAPAS) functions, including:

1. Implementing Correctional for Justice
2. Registration of Correctional Client
3. Conducting Community Guidance and Child Poverty
4. Following Judicial Sessions at the District Court and TPP Sessions (Correctional Observation Team) in Penal Institution in accordance with applicable laws and regulations
5. Provide guidance assistance to former prisoners, State children and correctional clients in need
6. Carry out the business of Breath Administration.

In providing its services, Correctional Hall (BAPAS) assigns correctional social work (PK) as spearheads of services to public penitentiary clients assisted by other professionals such as correctional social workers, social counselors, social psychologists, doctors, police, religious experts, economists and other practitioners.

In general, psychosocial problems are the conditions experienced by a person due to the disruption of social relationships, attitudes and behaviors that include disorders of thoughts, feelings, behaviors and or social relationships that continuously affect each other. The Correctional Social work (PK) has the responsibility for the success of the Social Reintegration program of the Client Prison in the family and community, so that the client can run the client's social functioning.

2. Discussion

2.1. Symptoms Related to Feelings (Affection)

- a. Experience a variety of negative emotions that had never, or seldom lived, such as anger, sadness, despair, loss of confidence, worries about the future.
- b. Feeling easily worried, afraid of things she had never feared before.
- c. Fear of things that can remind you of unpleasant events.
- d. Feeling sad about losing. Individuals are worried about losing again, worried that close and loved ones will die, will be separated from him.

2.2. Symptoms Related to Aspects of Cognition

- a. Negative evaluations of life, self-efficacy, goodwill and human capabilities in general.
- b. Often think of violent events (eg, events they experienced or witnessed) or obsessed with negative thoughts.
- c. Difficult to concentrate and difficult to be creative.
- d. Not interested in the activities he used to love.
- e. It is very difficult to make decisions even for simple things.

2.3. Symptoms Related to Actions or Behavior (Konasi)

- a. Displays behavioral changes, such as being angry, aggressive, withdrawing, ignoring others, being irresponsible, or otherwise being over protective in children, limiting family activity, becoming dependent and prosecuting.
 - b. Lack of excitement, loss of appetite
 - c. Restless, unable to sit still and unable to concentrate for longer periods of time
 - d. Especially in adolescents and young adults: excessive behavior to seek attention or to prove themselves, seek outflow, confusion and boredom through destructive behaviors that are detrimental to themselves or others (use of drugs, liquor, gambling, free sex, seizing and bullying others).
- 2.4. Symptoms Related to Physical Aspects
- a. Feeling unfit, lethargic, unhealthy.
 - b. Feeling a headache, nausea and vomiting, stomach pain, pain all over the body, heart beats very quickly and irregularly especially when feels frightened.
 - c. Sleeping problems: more frequent nightmares, easily awakened by the quiet noises, hard to sound, stay awake late into the night.
 - d. In children may appear symptoms of bedwetting, whereas previously never wet the bed.
- 2.5. Symptoms Related to Social Relations
- a. Irritable, angry and self-controlling, rude, conflicting with others.
 - b. Can not or hard to trust anyone else, being skeptical about everything.
 - c. Alone, rejecting social relationships.
 - d. Engage in a group that performs destructive actions by hurting yourself or others. Conducting activities that are high risk, defiant, drug addiction.
 - e. Social, moral, and behavioral concepts change. Revenge and fanaticism become very dominant in family life.

3. Implementation of Social Correctional Practice

3.1. Service Process

The client's intervention process begins when the client is at home. Correctional Social Work (PK) encounters clients as part of home visit activities escorted by a friend who happens to be next door to the client. The process of correctional social work practice conducted is:

1. Initial approach which includes Engagement, Intake and Contract

a. The initial approach is:

- 1) Involvement of a person in a situation, creating communication and formulating preliminary hypotheses recognizing the problem;
- 2) A period in which the correctional social worker (PK) begins to orient himself, especially regarding the tasks he takes care of;
- 3) Service and provision of resources for anyone who needs and qualify.

b. The duties of social workers in the early contact stage (engagement) are:

- 1) Engage himself in the situation;
- 2) Creating communication with everyone involved;
- 3) Start defining the size / parameter relating to the things to be implemented;
- 4) Create or create an initial / preliminary work structure.

c. Correctional social work (PK) have a responsibility to establish relationships with clients through:

- 1) The client comes voluntarily to ask for help (voluntary application). Clients are usually aware that they have a problem and try to resolve the problem in various ways but not / less successfully, so the client asks for help to correctional social workers.
 - 2) Clients do not want to come voluntarily (involuntary application). The client seeks to overcome the opposite of his desires because of the problems he encounters such as the social pressure of the individual / institution affecting him, but the client is reluctant to ask for help, the correctional social worker (PK) has the earliest task to connect and become acquainted with reluctance.
 - 3) Correctional social work (PK) trying to find clients. Social workers have a responsibility to help people with problems. Therefore the social worker will come out to involve himself or herself with someone who is not actively seeking help and not referral in order to get help.
- d. Contract (contract), is a formulation and preparation of work approval in order to facilitate the achievement of problem solving objectives. The contract is intended to create an agreement to understand the purpose of cooperation, methods, procedures, defining the role and duties of social workers and the role and duties of the client. Contracts can be formal or informal that are flexible and necessary to change lives through special relief relationships. The rationale is a pattern of partnership related to situations that require attention. The formulation or contracting is done on a reciprocal basis between social workers and clients.
2. Disclosure and understanding of the problem (assessment):
- Disclosure and understanding of the problem (an assessment) is an activity to understand the problems, client conditions, environment, and interaction of the three.
- The purpose of disclosure and understanding of the problem are:
- a. Help define the problem;
 - b. Demonstrate and connect resources according to problems and needs.
- Activities undertaken by social workers in the stage of disclosure and understanding of the problem are:
- 1). Data collection;
The important thing in data collection is to apply the principle whereby, the social worker only collects information relevant to the situation it handles and then formulates / formulates ways through valid assessment. Data sources are mainly obtained from clients and client systems. Sources of data can also be obtained from notes, reports, tests, studies and evaluations of issues related to client issues. It is done gradually, separately and simultaneously.
 - 2). Checking data
The thing that the social worker should pay attention to in collecting data is checking the data. Data checking is done to maintain the accuracy of data and information.
- c. Data analysis
Data analysis can be done if the data has been collected in a tested and measured to be completely objective.
- d. Conclusion
A conclusion can be obtained if the data analysis is done. Conclusions include:
- 1) Focus client issues
 - 2) client needs;
 - 3) Resources that can be utilized to solve the problem.
- To be able to carry out the functions and tasks of assessment well, social workers need to refer to the assessment principles. The social worker assessment will result in the uniqueness

and individualization of the problems, people, social situations and interactions among the three.

3. Preparation of Problem Solving Plan (Planning)

Preparation of a problem-solving plan (Planning) is the determination of the goal to direct the activity directly. Goal determination will be more effective if there is a division of processes, where clients have the primary responsibility to decide what needs and needs to be met and how to make it happen.

The process of goal setting is a reciprocal process in an effort to find the needs to be met and the actions that need to be taken to address the problem. Providing opportunities and responsibilities to clients will be able to increase their commitment in the problem-solving process. Clients will feel and believe that the goals that have been set really appropriate with the choice and relevant to the wishes. Objectives can provide meaning and direction for the problem-solving process and can be used as a guide and measure for the progress of the problem-solving process. Social workers need skills in motivating clients to be willing to actively select and formulate goals.

4. Troubleshooting (Intervention)

The handling of the problem in the practice of correctional social work (PK) is the action of correctional social work (PK) directed to the formulation that has been established in planning by using methods and techniques of correctional social work in accordance with the field of practice. Correctional social work (PK) must be able to change individual behavior as well as social environment condition.

5. Monitoring & Evaluation (Evaluation)

Correctional social work (PK) must be able to test efficacy (efficacy), the accuracy (accuracy) of alternative handling that is implemented also monitor the factors that bring success and which lead to failure. Correctional social work (PK) should develop strategies to enable the client to maintain the changes that he has achieved, the client is expected to maintain and enhance those changes by not displaying dysfunctional behavior after the relief is stopped.

6. Termination (Termination)

Termination is the process of terminating the service of the correctional social worker to the client. The terminations are conducted on the basis of a joint evaluation between the correctional social worker, the client, and other relevant parties regarding the outcomes achieved.

4. Issues Faced Clients / Client Problems

4.1. Short description of Client problems

Client is a citizen who is domiciled in Palembang, Client is a casual worker who have non permanent income since leaving from Penitentiary. Clients only have high school education, and since leaving the Penitentiary the client has no permanent job. This is because clients do not have special skills, work with odds. Client when can work work from morning until afternoon. After work sometimes clients attract motorcycles around his residence. Currently the client lives in a rented house residing in Palembang. Client inhabited the rented house is very narrow, and inhabited by 4 people who are clients, wives and their 2 children. The client's relationship with his wife and 2 children has an obstacle in communicating. Clients have shy, quiet and hard to get along with their neighbors, the client's age is not young anymore and has reached the age of 45 years.

Based on the brief description above, the correctional social workers identify the client's problems as follows:

1. Clients often move rented because each year rented increased the cost
2. Client often does not match neighbors
3. Clients shy, quiet and do not like to hang out with neighbors

In the implementation of client interventions, the process of correctional social work practice from the initial approach to the Termination. Correctional Social Work (PK) in the implementation of the process perform several roles in accordance with the needs that occur in solving client problems. The roles of social workers are:

a. Problem solver

Helping the client to find the way out of the problem so that found some alternative solutions.

Implementation:

Based on the assessment result, the correctional social work (PK) identifies client issues and then with clients and family makes efforts to overcome the problem:

- 1) Speaking with the clients, whether the client has a desire to stay settled in one rent for a long time.
- 2) Seek clients to participate in activities organized by the environment.
- 3) Frequent visits with neighbors.
- 4) Talking with your neighbors about issues about water, electricity, and so on.
- 5) Referring to health institutions related to client health issues, as well as seeking assistance for financing.

b. Motivator

Correctional Social Work (PK) plays a role to help clients give encouragement to arise awareness in the face of social problems and immediately implement its intention to seek alternative solutions.

Implementation:

- 1) Encouraging clients to approach the neighbors by doing silaturahmi. The first step of a correctional social work (PK) is accompanying the client when starting a conversation with his neighbor.
- 2) Encourage clients to look for materials when meeting with neighbors. Here the correctional social work (PK) helps by getting the client to see the neighbors' habits by talking to the neighbors so that the client can get into the topics that become his habit.
- 3) Encourage the clients to follow the activity of pengajian in environment. Through approaches to neighbors or people around clients, social workers ask to as often as possible to invite clients to follow the recitation.

c. Broker (Intermediary)

Correctional social work (PK) acts as a client liaison with source systems

Implementation:

Family Welfare Consultation Service: refers to the nearest LK3. Correctional social workers assist clients in obtaining Family Welfare Consultation Services. This is done to help clients get social counseling by social workers at the Family Welfare Consultation Institute to help clients get family and social guidance for clients.

5. Significant Changes On Clients During Services Directly

In the intervention process conducted by correctional social workers towards Palembang Correctional Hall (Bapas) clients, the results of the changes are:

In case the client is still in the process of follow-up:

1. Until now the client has performed health checks at community health centre has been done as much as 3 times. Clients are provided with social services to improve the client's social function.
2. Clients have started to follow pray together in the neighborhood where he lived today that invited by his neighbors.
3. Clients only occasionally mock, because of the night wind factor that causes clients often experience a cough.

6. Advanced Plan

6.1. Advanced plans with clients are:

1. Correctional Social Work (PK) with client will follow up if the result of the doctor's diagnosis shows that client must be given medical action to the hospital.
2. Correctional Social Work (PK) with clients regularly hold meetings to discuss progress achieved and things that still need to be addressed.

6.2. Obstacles In Implementation Of Palembang Correctional Hall (BAPAS) Services

There are several things that become obstacles in the implementation of Correctional Hall (BAPAS) services especially handle the client, among others:

1. The tendency of clients who survive in comfort zone, so it takes a long time in the services provided.
2. Changing the habits or properties of the client requires a long process, so the intensity of the presence of social workers is high enough to assist clients.

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